

Rice Breeding for Yield Improvement through Traditional and Modern Genetic Tools

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Abstract

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) stands as a paramount staple food, catering to the nutritional needs of over half of the world's population. Amidst burgeoning global demand and environmental challenges, the imperative to bolster rice yields has intensified. This abstract encapsulates the multifaceted approaches adopted in rice breeding to augment yield, encompassing both traditional methodologies and innovative transgenic techniques. Traditional breeding methods, honed over centuries, involve the meticulous selection of elite varieties based on desirable traits such as high yield potential, disease resistance, and adaptability to diverse agro-climatic conditions. Through conventional breeding, breeders have successfully developed improved rice varieties with enhanced yield potential, contributing significantly to global food security. In parallel, the advent of transgenic technology has revolutionized rice breeding by enabling the precise manipulation of genetic material to confer desired traits. Transgenic approaches facilitate the introduction of genes associated with traits such as pest resistance, abiotic stress tolerance, and increased photosynthetic efficiency, thereby elevating yield potential and resilience in rice cultivars. Despite controversies surrounding genetically modified organisms (GMOs), transgenic rice varieties have demonstrated promising results in field trials, offering novel solutions to address pressing agricultural challenges.

Keywords: *rice yields, breeding, disease resistance, adaptability, global food security, agricultural challenges.*

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Introduction

Rice breeding stands as a cornerstone in the quest for enhancing global food security, particularly through the refinement of yield-focused methodologies. Traditional breeding methods, rooted in centuries of agricultural practice, have provided a solid foundation for cultivar improvement. Concurrently, transgenic approaches have emerged, leveraging cutting-edge genetic engineering to introduce novel traits and bolster productivity. This dynamic blend of traditional wisdom and modern innovation underscores a multifaceted pursuit aimed at addressing the pressing challenges of feeding a growing population amidst environmental fluctuations. In this introduction, we embark on a journey delving into the intricacies of rice breeding, exploring its traditional and transgenic facets, and the synergistic potential they hold for advancing agricultural sustainability and resilience. Rice breeders have a set of techniques to boost yields through harnessing the power of genetics.

Here are some key strategies:

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Conventional Hybridization

This time-tested technique in which crossing of two rice plants having favorable traits are crossed. Only the offspring leading to high yield will be selected.

For yield improvement Conventional breeding plays a crucial role by incorporating desirable traits and characteristics into new varieties. Here are several ways conventional breeding can enhance rice yield:

Disease and pest Resistance: Some rice varieties having high yield potential are unable to produce high yield due to susceptibility to any disease and pest. Breeders can develop rice varieties that are resistant to various diseases and pest such as blast, bacterial blight, sheath blight, stem borers and leaf folders etc. Resistant rice plants are less likely to suffer yield losses, leading to higher yields.

Abiotic Stress Tolerance: Conventional breeding can produce rice varieties that are tolerant to abiotic stresses such as drought, salinity, and high temperatures. These stress-tolerant varieties can maintain productivity under adverse environmental conditions, ensuring more stable yields.

Improved Nutrient Uptake: Plant having good efficiency to use nutrients produce high yield. Breeding programs focus on enhancing the nutrient uptake and utilization efficiency in rice plants. Varieties with improved nutrient uptake can achieve better growth, development, and ultimately higher yields.

Enhanced Yield Components: Conventional breeding aims to improve yield components like grain size, number of grains per panicle, and panicle size. Varieties with larger grains and more grains per panicle can significantly increase overall yield per unit area.

Early Maturity: Developing rice varieties with shorter growth durations can allow farmers to cultivate multiple crops in a year, especially in regions with favorable growing conditions. Early-maturing varieties enable quicker turnaround times and higher annual yields.

Adaptation to Specific Environments: Breeding efforts target specific agro-ecological zones to develop rice varieties adapted to local conditions. Varieties tailored to specific environments exhibit better performance and yield stability, supporting sustainable agriculture practices.

Quality Traits: Apart from yield, breeding also emphasizes improving quality traits such as grain appearance, cooking characteristics, and nutritional content. High-quality rice varieties fetch better prices in the market, providing additional incentives for farmers.

Overall, conventional breeding in rice plays a pivotal role in enhancing yield potential by integrating a diverse range of genetic traits and characteristics that collectively contribute to improved productivity, resilience, and profitability for farmers (Ul-Allah *et al.*, 2023).

Ideotype Breeding

In ideotype breeding, breeders prioritize traits crucial for yield potential such as disease resistance, stress tolerance (e.g., drought or salinity tolerance), lodging resistance, nutrient efficiency, photosynthetic efficiency, and optimal plant architecture. This approach focuses on designing ideal plant structures with features like sturdy stems to prevent lodging, balanced tillering capacity, appropriate leaf morphology for efficient photosynthesis, and robust root systems for nutrient uptake. Environmental adaptation is key, with traits tailored to specific conditions; for instance, drought-tolerant traits are emphasized in drought-prone areas. The result is enhanced productivity and resilience, exemplified by Sub1 rice varieties engineered by IRRI for submergence tolerance, showcasing the success of ideotype breeding in improving rice yield under stress conditions. (Bhanu *et al.*, 2016).

Heterosis Breeding

This strategy exploits a phenomenon called hybrid vigor. By crossing genetically diverse rice lines, breeders can create offspring (hybrids) with significantly higher yields compared to their parents. This

approach relies on a specific type of sterility in one parent line to control seed production. (Ouyang et al., 2022). In some traits negative heterosis contribute in yield enhancement of rice hybrid. Like plant height, dwarf plant has tolerance to lodging lead to increase in yield.

Breeders strategically select diverse parent lines to create hybrids with complementary traits, such as strong tillering and larger grains. Challenges include maintaining consistent high yield in subsequent generations, often requiring complex pollination control systems like the "three-line system." Despite hurdles, heterosis breeding has significantly increased rice yields, particularly in Asia, making it crucial for areas with intensive agriculture and emphasizing its substantial impact on global rice production.

Wide Hybridization

Wide breeding, also known as wide hybridization, introduces novel genetic variation into rice varieties by incorporating genes from wild relatives or other rice species. (Gaikwad et al., 2021). This genetic diversity can encompass traits such as biotic and abiotic stress tolerance, enhanced nutrient use efficiency, and other important agronomic characteristics. One significant outcome of wide breeding is the development of rice varieties with enhanced stress tolerance, as wild relatives often possess natural resistance to pests, diseases, drought, salinity, and flooding. By crossing cultivated rice with these wild relatives, breeders can transfer genes for stress tolerance, leading to the creation of resilient rice varieties. This optimization results in better growth, development, and ultimately higher yields. This approach reduces yield losses due to diseases and minimizes the reliance on chemical control methods, enhancing the overall productivity and sustainability of rice cultivation.

Transgenic-free rice was developed by segregating out the transgene with self-fertilization in the T1 generation (Xu et al., 2015).

Crop Rotation and Diversification

Rotate rice with other crops to break pest and disease cycles, improve soil health, and enhance overall productivity. Diversification can also provide additional income streams for farmers (Chittapur et al., 2017).

Post-Harvest Management

Proper post-harvest handling, storage, and processing can reduce losses and maintain grain quality, ensuring that maximum yield potential is realized from the harvested crop.

Marker Assisted Selection (MAS) and Genomic Selection

A genome map serves as a navigational reference point and helps locate specific features on chromosomes, making it an essential tool for gene identification, species comparison, and genome sequencing. The meiotic genetic recombination frequency of rice indicates that the genome, which consists of 12 chromosomes, is roughly 1500 cM long, or 430 Mb in total length (Uike et al., 2024). Global and local genomes are used in genomics research to study molecular, chromosomal, biochemical, and phenotypic levels.

Marker assisted selection (MAS) use DNA/RNA variation, biochemical and morphological marker to select a trait or genetic determinant (Lantos et al., 2023). MAS was initially introduced by Smith and Simpson (1986) and Soller and Beckmann (1990). Since 1996, Hokkaido's rice breeding programs have employed marker assisted selection (MAS), first for research and genotypes and phenotypes was utilized to identify genetic markers associated with traits (Fujino et al., 2019). Molecular markers are DNA fragments that are connected with certain sites in the genome and divided into two types: PCR-based markers (AFLP, SNP, RAPD, SCAR, SSR, CAPS, STS, and DART) and hybridization-based markers (RFLP and minisatellites). Among these markers are amplified fragment length polymorphism (AFLP),

expressed sequence tags (EST), sequence tagged sites (STS), restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP), and simple sequence repeat (SSR).

Essential marker assisted strategies in plant breeding are marker-assisted backcross breeding (MABB), marker assisted gene pyramiding (MAGP) and marker assisted recurrent selection (MARS). When MABB occurs, the most significant gene from a substandard source is incorporated into the elite cultivar. Gene pyramiding occurs when genes are transferred from multiple progenitors into a single genotype. Gene pyramiding is an approach utilized to enhance characteristics that are challenging to quantify via traditional breeding methods. It involves the use of functional markers to identify genes that influence particular characteristics. Near-isogenic lines (NILs), which are backcrossing mapping populations formed by mating the donor carrying the desired trait with the recurrent parent. NILs are employed in breeding programmes to map quantitative trait loci (QTLs) and markers associated with target genes. They are utilised to pyramid QTLs and investigate epistatic interactions among genes.

The MAS method is implemented in order to reduce reproduction time, population size, and generations. MAS improves the efficacy of plant breeding by facilitating target gene introgression and recovery via backcrossing (Kumar et al., 2022). Five biotic stress resistance genes inserted into the japonica rice cultivar via MAS by Suh et al. (2015). Using closely linked PCR-based DNA markers, two recessive (xa5 and xa13) and one dominant (Xa21). Bacterial leaf blight (BLB) resistant genes were inserted into the BPT5204 genetic background in rice via biotechnology tools. SCU-Rice-SSR 1 is a co-dominant PCR-based marker, and two SSR markers, SCU015RM (4 cM) and SCU017RM, have been found for aroma testing in basmati rice.

Breeding for Yield Improvement

The grain number is the most important attribute because it is directly related to yield. Introducing high grain number genes, or QTLs, such as Gn1, rg5, and APO1, into premier rice cultivars can boost food supply (Gouda et al., 2019). Alleles that are beneficial for grain number on chromosomes 5, 8, and 9 have been discovered. Map-based cloning found a cytokinin oxidase gene with improved grain number and yield (Gouda et al., 2020). Hap-3 haplotypes (Ma et al. 2019) and GS-3 (Nan et al. 2018) can be used in MAS to improve yield. Utilizing the Advance Backcross QTL (ABQTL) technique, rice researchers have identified QTLs with favorable effects on agronomic factors derived from wild species (Gouda et al., 2020). A single variety can be swiftly enriched with genes/QTLs using MAS, satisfying human demand. Molecular breeding generates NILs, RILs, and BIL populations, which aid in QTL and gene identification, resulting in increased grain output and crop stress tolerance.

Hybridization and Its Role in Improving Yield and Diseased Resistance

Hybrid rice technology, developed in China by LP Yuan in the 1970s, has showed promise for commercializing rice production and overcoming yield stability concerns. A DNA marker-based technique can replace the traditional Grow-Out Test (GOT), allowing hybrid rice breeders and seed businesses to monitor parental and hybrid seed purity rapidly and reliably. Understanding the genetics of fertility restoration across sites, as well as finding markers connected to these genes, can significantly improve the efficiency of restorative breeding and the production of new restorer lines from germplasm. Seven TGMS genes have been molecularly mapped, using marker assisted selection as a viable option for transferring these genes to desirable genetic backgrounds.

Biotechnological Tools such as CRISPR/Case9 for Targeted Gene Editing

Rice biotechnology has gained momentum since the mid-1980s, allowing molecular biology tools to unravel genetic information such as insect resistance and enhanced nutrition in rice genomes (Mitiku et

al., 2022). In 2002, rice became the first crop whose genome was decoded. Genome-editing techniques such as CRISPR-Cas9 have enabled precise genetic changes for resistance to environmental stress and disease (Jemal et al., 2022). CRISPR/Cas9 plant genome editing was first reported in 2013 for monocotyledonous crop plants, including wheat and rice (Qiu et al., 2013). Resistance to fungus and bacteriophages developed by combining disease-specific protein and CP genes OsSSI2 (Jiang et al., 2020). TALEN technology was utilized to target the bacterial blight susceptibility gene Os11N3 in *Oryza sativa*, producing disease-resistant rice (Li et al., 2012). Rice blast resistance was enhanced by using a CRISPR/Cas9 SSN (C-ERF922) that targeted the OsERF922 transcription factor gene in rice. Golden rice, a genetically engineered crop, was created in the early 2000s to address vitamin A deficiency (Potrykus, 2001).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the pursuit of enhancing rice yield through traditional and transgenic breeding approaches represents a critical endeavor in securing global food security amidst the challenges of population growth, climate change, and diminishing agricultural land. Traditional breeding methods have laid the foundation for centuries, leveraging natural genetic variability to develop improved rice varieties tailored to diverse agro-climatic conditions. These methods, albeit time-consuming, have yielded significant successes, demonstrating resilience, adaptability, and enhanced yields. Concurrently, transgenic approaches, enabled by advancements in biotechnology, offer novel solutions to complement traditional breeding efforts. Genetic modification holds the promise of precise manipulation of specific traits, such as disease resistance, abiotic stress tolerance, and nutritional content, thereby accelerating the development of high-yielding rice cultivars. However, the adoption of transgenic rice varieties is not without challenges, including regulatory hurdles, public perception, and potential ecological impacts, necessitating thorough risk assessment and transparent communication. Moreover, the integration of traditional and transgenic breeding strategies presents a synergistic approach, harnessing the strengths of each method to maximize yield gains sustainably. Collaborative efforts between scientists, breeders, policymakers, and farmers are imperative to navigate the complexities of rice breeding, ensuring equitable access to improved varieties and promoting agroecological resilience. As we stand at the nexus of technological innovation and agricultural sustainability, it is paramount to prioritize research investments, foster interdisciplinary collaborations, and uphold ethical considerations to harness the full potential of rice breeding for global food security. By embracing a holistic approach that balances scientific rigor, socio-economic inclusivity, and environmental stewardship, we can chart a path towards a future where rice production is not only enhanced but also equitable, resilient, and sustainable for generations to come.

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